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Impact of Aggressive Communication Styles of School Heads on Teachers' Emotional Stress at Secondary Schools in Bannu District

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was; to investigate Communication Styles of School Heads and Their Influence on Teachers' Emotional Stress at secondary level in Bannu District. The study was descriptive in nature so descriptive survey design was used by the researcher to conduct the study. The study was descriptive in nature so descriptive survey design was used by the researcher to conduct the study. All 130 (Male/Female) secondary schools and all 1627(Male/Female) secondary schools' teachers working in secondary schools of Bannu district was the population of the study. Stratified random sampling technique was used to draw sample for the study. The sample size was justified by using Krejice& Morgan (1970) formula. The sample of the study was comprised of 56 secondary schools and 327 secondary school male and female teachers working in secondary schools in Bannu District. Two Questionnaires for the teachers were used to collect data from the sampled respondents. The collected data was analyzed by using Mean, Standard deviation. Regression used to find out required findings and conclusions. The study found that school heads commonly used average levels of both passive and aggressive communication styles, which significantly contributed to emotional stress among secondary school teachers. Regression analysis confirmed a notable statistical relationship between these communication behaviors and teacher well-being, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Aggressive communication had a slightly stronger impact, though both styles proved detrimental. In light of these findings, it is recommended that school systems prioritize the enhancement of leadership communication through targeted training, feedback mechanisms, and policy reforms.

Key Words: Schools Heads, Aggressive Communication Styles, Teachers' Emotional Stress at Secondary level, Bannu

INTRODUCTION

Communicative preferences are significant factors in almost every aspect of school life. School processes may be analyzed and understood through the lens of communication styles, and communication styles can be used to affect the actions and understandings of others. School Heads' and teachers often have several meetings, chats, and interaction during the course of a typical workday. The emotional stress of teachers is considered to be significantly influenced by the communication patterns of school heads'. In successful schools, the rapport between teachers and the head is crucial. It is crucial that the school head be able to effectively communicate with the teachers. The term "school climate" is often used to describe how schools operate. (Izhak, 2017)

There are many ways to put into words what's going on in our heads and hearts. As a leader, it's essential to keep in mind that communication encompasses more than just words, including nonverbal cues like body language and facial emotions. (Fellow.app 2020)

As a school head, if you want your staff to be effective, happy, and productive, you need to know how to deal with them who have diverse communication preferences. (Fellow.app 2020)

Statement of the Problem

The school heads' has a significant impact on the emotional stress experienced by the teachers. Teachers remember favorably if they are impressed by his or her communication style. Teachers' work satisfaction and emotional well-being are negatively impacted by the leadership team's ability to effectively communicate with their teachers. The emotional stress of teachers is increasingly attributable to the communication styles of school heads'. It's possible that the position of school heads will vary from institution to institution due to the fact that heads have varying approaches to communicating. There is a lack of interaction, harmony, trust, and cooperation between heads and teachers in many dimensions. To abridge this gap there is a dire need to conduct a study on the impact school heads aggressive communication style on teachers emotional stress at secondary level of district Bannu. So that school heads and teachers cooperation may provide better educational outcomes..

Research Objectives

The following were the objectives of the study:

1. To identify communication styles of the school heads at secondary level in Bannu District.
2. To investigate the level of emotional stress of teachers at secondary level.
3. To compare emotional stress of male and female teachers in secondary schools.
4. To compare school heads' communication styles by gender.
5. To investigate the impact of school heads' communication styles on teachers' emotional stress.

Research Questions

The following were the research questions of the study:

1. What communication styles are used by school heads at secondary level?
2. What is the level of emotional stress of teachers at secondary level?

Null Hypothesis:

The following were the Null Hypothesis of the study

H₀ 1: There is no statistical difference between male and female teachers regarding their aggressive communication style of their heads.

H₀ 2: There is no statistical difference between male and female teachers regarding their emotional stress.

H₀ 3: There is no statistical impact of school heads' communication styles on teachers' emotional stress at secondary level.

Significance of the study

This study was defensible on the following grounds:

Present study was the first one which investigates impact of school heads' communication styles on teachers' emotional stress at secondary level. This study would contribute useful information that which communication styles of the school heads' effect on teachers' emotional stress.

The findings of the study would highlight "Impact of the communication styles of school heads' on teachers' emotional stress of Government Boys'/Girls' High Schools in Bannu District and the recommendations of the study would be helpful in providing guidelines to the schools heads' to improve their communication styles with the teachers such as talking, listening, good relationship and behavior.

Delimitations of the study

The study was delimited to Public Secondary Schools of District Bannu. The study was also delimited to aggressive communication style.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This portion deals with review of available literature related to the study. The chief purpose of the study was; Impact of Schools Heads' Communication Styles on Teachers' Emotional Stress at Secondary Level" is reviewed here.

Aggressive Communication

Hwang (2016) argues that aggressive communication entails expressing one's views and ideas directly and forcefully. Clients were educated on the many dimensions of verbal aggression (such as yelling, demanding, commanding, blaming, condemning, and harming others with words). The fact that abuse might manifest itself physically (by means of, for example, shoving, beating, slapping, or otherwise aggressively assaulting another person) was also underlined. The prior chapter's query, "why don't you ever do the dishes?" may now be extended to include more strenuous behaviours like throwing dishes or punching oneself or others. The characteristics of aggressive communication include its inefficiency, dominance, and conflict. The many different responses people might have when confronted with aggression was a topic covered in client education. In instance, some people may take an antagonistic stance and refuse to hear you out. They may first comply with your requests, but eventually come to despise you and blow. Some individuals may be reluctant to tell you how they really feel because of the potential for unpleasant outcomes. Their response might be hostile, resulting in heated arguments or even physical violence.

Types of Communication

There are three distinct modes of interaction in the world, as described by Daniel Chandler (2011). We can express ourselves verbally, nonverbally, and in writing.

Verbal Communication

Danesi, Marcel (2000), states that verbal communication is the transfer of information by spoken or written means. The grammars (laws) by which these symbols are modified may be thought of as the building blocks of human language. The term "language" may also be used to refer to characteristics shared by several

tongues. In most cases, a person's ability to acquire a new language is at its peak during their formative years. The vast majority of the world's languages rely on sonic or gestural patterns to represent symbols that allow speakers to convey meaning to one another. There are common characteristics shared by most languages; nevertheless, there are always outliers. Human languages are not the only possible basis for constructed languages like Esperanto, computer languages, and numerous mathematical formalisms.

Language features adhere to a set of norms. There are laws for every aspect of language, from the sounds that make up words and phrases to how sentences are structured and punctuated to the meanings conveyed by those words and phrases.

Words may have either their literal, or denotative, meanings, which refer to the subject matter at hand, or their more nuanced, or connotative, meanings, which consider the speakers' connections with one another as well as their emotions, backgrounds, and positions of the communicators.

However, the sign vocabulary, syntax, and other linguistic structures of ASL and other signed languages across the globe adhere to all the required categories as spoken languages; therefore they are recognized to constitute verbal communication. However, the pace, intensity, and magnitude of the signals used are all examples of nonverbal components that contribute to the meaning of signed languages. In answer to a query, a signer could sign "yes," or they might sign "yes" slowly and sarcastically. The word "yes" is represented by the sign, while the other actions provide further nonverbal context.

Non-verbal communication

"Nonverbal communication is that kind of procedures which communicates such information in the shape of non-linguistic representations," writes Marcel Danesi (2013). Nonverbal communication encompasses everything from haptic communication and chronemic communication through gestures, body language, facial expressions, eye contact, and so on. It is not always necessary to use words to express meaning. Both overt gestures like hand-shaking and winking, and more subtle cues like perspiring may convey meaning. Paralanguage describes the aspects of communication other than words that are equally important. Subtly, it affects people's ability to confide in one another and talk to one another. Nonverbal indicators like calligraphy style and word space serve the same purpose in written texts.

Paul

Watzlawick's (1969) rules are shown by the ineffectiveness of nonverbal communication. Once an organism develops a sense of consciousness, it can respond to and make sense of incoming information. Complement, exemplify, reinforce, substitute, govern, regulate, and contradict the denotative message—these are only some of the roles that nonverbal communication plays in human interaction.

Words

aren't always necessary; nonverbal clues may stand in for or supplement them while communicating with others. However, non-verbal cues might be difficult to interpret. Rather of blindly trusting a person's words when they seem to contradict their actions, we look to their non-verbal cues to determine what they're really thinking and feeling.

Several

factors contribute to the significance of non-verbal cues in human interaction:

It's impossible to avoid nonverbal cues. Each and every one of our acts of communication contains them. Interactions face-to-face require the use of all available

non-verbal channels for complete communication. These include the body, face, voice, look, touch, space, time, and other ecological variables. There may be non-verbal aspects to written communication as well. It is possible to include non-verbal clues into written communication by modifying text font colour, stationery, adding emoticons, capitalization, and photos in e-mails, online chats, and social media. Nonverbal acts serve a variety of purposes. Communication actions use several non-verbal channels at once, increasing the possibility of sending and receiving signals at the same time.

There may be one common language based on non-verbal cues. People of all backgrounds employ and understand common non-verbal behaviour such as laughing, weeping, pointing, stroking, and staring.

When verbal communication is hindered by a language barrier, the simplest form of communication may be established via the use of such non-verbal cues.

Written communication

The development of new technologies has resulted in new ways of communicating and new ways of thinking about communication. Emerging fields of study like media psychology and communications psychology are examples of these developments. According to (Lyons, John 1981)

There have been three major shifts in the dissemination of information that have influenced the development of written communication.

Pictographs were the first form of written language. Since the pictograms were carved in stone, it was not yet possible to take textual communication with you. The complexity of pictograms was reduced as they became more standardized.

The second phase was the development of movable alphabets once writing methods were adopted and used on different mediums like as paper, papyrus, clay, and wax. The ability to communicate while on the go emerged.

The third and final phase involves the transmission of data through electrical signals and regulated waves of electromagnetic radiation.

The goal of every kind of communication is to establish a common ground from which to build understanding. Tautology replication throughout the cosmos is what Gregory Bateson dubbed it. Facilitating communication between people calls for a wide range of abilities, including the ability to listen, observe, talk, question, analyze, gesture, and evaluate.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Methodology part consist of procedure and pattern of the study. The researcher does effort to explain related procedure and method for the documentation of this study which are given below.

Research Design

Leedy and Ormrod (2005) say that research is a viable approach to a problem only when there is data to support it. A research design is the plan or proposed to conduct a research. According to Creswell and Creswell (2017), quantitative research is the investigation into human or social problems. To status that quantitative research aims to determine the relationship between an independent and dependent variable in a population by gathering data and numerically analyzing this relationship. The study was descriptive in nature. Therefore, the researcher used survey method design for analysis.

Population

The population of the study was comprised of all Government Boys' and Girls High Schools' teachers (N=1637; ASCR 2020-21) working in public secondary schools in District Bannu of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Table No. 1: Number of Teachers as Population at Secondary Schools

District	Boys	Girls	Total
Bannu	1068	569	1637

(EMIS, 2020, 21)

Sampling and Sample Size

Sampling is the process of selecting a subset of a population to serve as a stand-in for the whole. The sample is a subset of the population that accurately represents the whole. (Lance, Hattori, 2016). Using an online sample calculator (<http://www.surveysystem.com>), a sample size of N=1637 was determined to achieve a 0.05 level of significance with 95 percent confidence. After that, a simple random sample method (found at <https://stattrek.com/survey-research/basic-random-sampling.aspx>) was used to choose the participants. The researcher utilized a stratified random sampling method since it would have been unreasonable to choose an equal number of male and female teachers.

Table No.2: Number of Teachers as Sample at Secondary Schools

District	Male	Female	Total
Bannu	220	107	327

Curry, et al. (2013)

Male size == $NN = 327 / 1637 = 220$

Female size == $NN = 327 / 1637 = 107$

Curry, L.A., ET AL (2013) explain the sample size Rule of Thumb as below

The population Size			The Sample Dimension
101	To	1,000	10%
1,001	To	5,000	5%
5,001	To		3%
10,000+			1%

Research Instruments

Self-developed two questionnaires (communication style questionnaire and Teachers' emotional stress questionnaire) were used for data collection. The instruments were consisted of 5 points based on the popular Likert's scale. The response category was varied from "Never to Always." Classification of Mean: 1. 0 to 2.49 is below Average 2. 2.50 to 3.49 is Average ,3. 3.50 to 5.00 is above Average. Therefore, both of the questionnaires were considered suitable and valid instruments. Five point Likert scale was used.

Never	Seldom	Occasionally	Frequently	Always
1	2	3	4	5

Validity and Reliability

For the validation of the both of the questionnaires, the researcher requested a panel of experts to refine the items, in order to make the questionnaires simple and understandable. In the light of feedback received from the experts, the questionnaires were finalized. For determining the reliability of this instrument, 30 respondents were selected. Cronbach's Alpha was applied to calculate internal consistency of items.

Validation of the Questionnaires

The validation of the questionnaires is extremely essential and used for collection of information. Therefore, it is essential to grip the accuracy as well as precise information. Then, "the researcher took 5 experts' views for content validity of the questionnaires. In these four experts were from Peshawar University and one was from UST Bannu.

Reliability of the Questionnaires

Consistency of the Questionnaires is extremely significant work during instrumentation. Consistent of questionnaires provides accurate as well as precise information. For the rationale of the consistency the investigator took 30 respondents. The investigator took respondents' views on Likert-Type scale, i-e "Never", "Seldom", "Occasionally", "Frequently", "Always." The views of the respondents set into "software package for the social science" "SPSS" Version 23. Intended for examination of the consistency of the both Questionnaires Cronbach's Alpha formula was used. In general the reliabilities less than 0.6 are considered to be poor, those in the 0.70 range are acceptable, and those over 0.8 are considered good George and Mallery (2003) gave these rules of thumb: ">.9 =Excellent, > .8 = Good, > .7 = Acceptable, >.6 = Questionable, > .5 = Poor, and < .5 = Unacceptable".

Method of Data collection

In general, the researcher got permission from school principals and the district education officer. To guarantee conformity with ethical norms, the researcher obtained prior and informed consent. Keeping in mind the local traditions, the researcher collected data directly from male respondents and indirectly from female respondents. The procedure of compilation of information was appropriately organized and respondents took the responsibility and filled the questionnaires which were returned on time.

Data Analysis Techniques

The collected data were put in "SPSS-23" used for treatment. To find out the answer for objective number one, i-e school heads' communication styles and two and i-e teachers emotional stress mean, standard deviation, as well as Mann-Whitney U- test was used. To assess the impact' linear regression was also used.

ANALYSIS AND INTREPRETATION OF DATA

This part deals with the collection and analysis of the data. The primary data were obtained through Questionnaires, which was fielded to the respondents in district Bannu. The data were analyzed with the help of tables and converted into percentages for discussion and interpretation. The following tables were used to interpret the descriptive analysis.

Research Question 1:What communication styles are used by school heads at secondary level?

Table 4: shows School Heads' Aggressive Communication Style item wise Mean and Standard Deviation

S.#	Statement	Total	M	SD
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1	The head ignores situation which needs solution on urgent basis.	327	3.77	.85
2	The head regularly uses aggressive means of communication.	327	2.72	.74
3	He/She does not listen to others.	327	2.84	.87
4	He/She uses harsh language in meetings.	327	2.49	.62
5	He/She keeps deep eyes contact with others.	327	2.66	.81
6	He/She shows unlikeness when others do not confirm his/her opinions.	327	2.59	.60
7	He/She does not seek the opinions of others where needed.	327	2.56	.62
8	He/She least bothers others opinions irrespective of opposition by his/her colleagues.	327	2.98	.85
9	When something does not go right, he/she blames others.	327	2.18	1.10

Table 4.2 illustrates Mean scores of Aggressive Communication Styles items in the scale fall in the average Mean category 2.50 to 3.49, showing that Aggressive communication styles of school heads are not up to the mark in all phase.

Research Question 2: What is the level of emotional stress of teachers at secondary level?

Table 5: Teachers' Emotional Stress at secondary level statement wise Mean and Standard Deviation

S.#	Statement	N	M	SD
1.	I feel stress when too many work demands are being made on me	327	2.36	0.58
2.	I feel stress when I take extra classes.	327	2.78	0.75
3.	I feel stress when I teach in noisy conditions.	327	2.86	0.97
4.	I feel stress in meetings with school head when he does not properly listen to me.	327	2.72	0.70
5.	I become stress when the school head negatively criticizes my work.	327	2.80	0.76
6.	The head inappropriate attitude stresses me.	327	2.11	0.78
7.	I feel stress when I teach to overcrowded classes.	327	2.36	0.57
8.	I feel stress when there is a lack of coordination between me and the school head.	327	2.64	0.70
9.	Poor working conditions in school stress me.	327	2.84	0.78
10.	Poor communication skills of head stress me.	327	2.62	0.76
11.	I feel stress when the head does not give importance to my opinions in the school matter	327	2.54	0.68
12.	I feel stress when head does not acknowledge my services.	327	2.42	0.85
13.	I become stressed when the head uses harsh language in staff meeting.	327	2.32	0.69
14.	I feel stress when head does not openly speak about any matter.	327	2.79	0.84

15.	The heads' unpleasant facial expression stresses me.	327	2.88	0.91
16.	I feel stress when the head gives me a short deadline about some work.	327	2.53	0.71
17.	I become emotionally stress when the head undermines my job performance.	327	2.58	0.66
18.	I feel stress when the head frequently reminds me my previous mistakes.	327	2.33	0.60
19.	Inadequate physical facilities in school make me stress.	327	2.26	0.89
20.	I become stress when the head taunts me on small issues.	327	2.31	0.96
21.	Students' misbehavior in class makes me stress.	327	2.84	0.76
22.	Poor working relationship with head make me stress.	327	2.13	0.78
23.	Lack of professional development opportunities make me stress.	327	2.88	0.77
24.	I feel stress when the head does not include me in decision making.	327	2.31	0.74
25.	Incompetent clerical staff behavior makes me stress.	327	2.95	0.94
26.	I feel stress when the head does not communicate us the exam schedule on time.	327	2.16	0.99
27.	I feel stress when I teach in unsuitable thermal conditions.	327	2.95	0.91
28.	The head poor eye contact stresses me.	327	2.82	0.71
29.	I feel stress when the head does not communicate classes' timetable on time.	327	2.89	0.88

Table 5 illustrates mean scores of emotional stress items in the scale fall in the average Mean category 2.50 to 3.49, showing that teachers' emotional stress not up to the mark in all phase.

H₀ 2: There is no statistical difference between male and female teachers regarding their aggressive communication style of their heads.

Table No. 6 Gender wise Aggressive Style

Category	Respondents	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mann-Whitney U test	P-value
1	Male	219	25.95	2.69	11482.500	.717
2	Female	107	26.01	2.65		

Table N. 6 shows sample sizes, standard deviation, U-test and p-value for both male and female groups. After checking the normality we can applied non parametric test alternative to t test which is Mann Whitney u test. The mean of male is 25.95 and female mean is 26.01, standard deviation for male is 2.69 and female is 2.65. The U-test is 11482.500 and the p-value is .717. Since p-value is greater than 0.5 it indicates that null hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is no significance difference between both groups regarding aggressive style of communication.

H₀ 2: There is no statistical difference between male and female teachers regarding their emotional stress.

Hypotheses 3: There is no statistical impact of school heads' communication styles on teachers' emotional stress at secondary level.

Table: Regression Coefficients Summary

Predictor Variable	Unstandardized Coefficient	SE	β	t-value	p-value
Constant	1.267	0.143	—	8.860	0.000
ACS	0.427	0.069	0.354	6.188	0.000

The un-standardized coefficients further indicate that for every one-unit increase in aggressive communication style leads to a 0.427-unit increase in emotional stress. Given the F-value of 96.234 and the overall model significance ($p = 0.000$), the regression model is statistically valid and reliable. These results lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis, confirming that the aggressive communication style of school heads have a measurable and significant impact on teachers' emotional well-being.

Model Summary

R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F-value	Sig. (p)
0.611	0.373	0.369	96.234	0.000

The model yielded an R² value of 0.373, indicating that approximately 37.3% of the variance in teachers' emotional stress can be explained by the influence of aggressive communication styles. Both predictors were statistically significant at $p < 0.05$, with aggressive communication style ($\beta = 0.354$, $t = 6.188$, $p = 0.000$) showing a slightly stronger standardized effect than passive communication style ($\beta = 0.312$, $t = 5.333$, $p = 0.000$). This suggests that as the intensity of either communication style increases, so does the level of stress experienced by teachers.

FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This part deals with results, discussion, conclusions and recommendations of the study:

Results

The study found that the aggressive communication styles were also reported at an average level among school heads. Teachers perceived that school heads occasionally used harsh language, ignored others' opinions, and placed blame on subordinates. The data indicated that while aggression was not dominant, it occurred frequently enough to contribute to an uncomfortable or stressful work environment for teachers.

The study also revealed that teachers experienced an average level of emotional stress. This stress was linked to several factors including workload, lack of acknowledgment from school heads, poor communication, and mismanagement in daily school operations. Teachers frequently reported feeling disregarded and unsupported, which contributed to their overall emotional strain.

Regression analysis indicated a statistically significant impact of aggressive communication styles on teachers' emotional stress. Aggressive communication had

a slightly stronger influence, which was substantial predictor. This highlighted that the way school heads communicated had a measurable effect on the psychological state of their teaching staff.

Based on the regression model, approximately one-third of the variance in teachers' emotional stress could be explained by the communication styles of their school heads. This emphasized the central role of leadership behavior in influencing teacher well-being. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected, confirming that school heads' communication styles significantly impacted teachers' emotional stress levels at the secondary level.

Discussion

The findings of this study align with recent literature emphasizing the critical role of leadership communication in the emotional well-being of teachers. According to Akinyemi et al. (2023), effective school leadership that fosters transparent, respectful, and supportive communication is positively correlated with reduced teacher burnout and enhanced job satisfaction. The current study's revelation that both passive and aggressive communication styles elevate stress among teachers reinforces the view that inappropriate communication, whether avoidant or confrontational, disrupts the school climate.

Aggressive communication, which showed a slightly stronger effect on stress, often includes behaviors such as criticism, sarcasm, or authoritative dominance. These behaviors have been found to erode trust and increase feelings of helplessness among subordinates (Lee & Kim, 2022). Teachers under such leadership may feel devalued and micromanaged, leading to emotional exhaustion. Passive communication, on the other hand, though less directly harmful, creates confusion and lack of direction, which also contributes to chronic stress (Zhou et al., 2021).

The findings further support transformational leadership theory, which advocates for clear, empathetic, and empowering communication as a tool to inspire and emotionally support team members (Bass & Riggio, 2006). In contrast, the communication styles identified in this study did not align with such leadership practices. Both passive and aggressive styles reflect elements of transactional or laissez-faire leadership, which have been shown to have a negative impact on teachers' motivation and well-being (Eyal & Roth, 2019).

The significance of the regression model indicates that school heads' communication behavior should not be overlooked in education reform discussions. As suggested by Khanal et al. (2022), emotional health in educational settings is heavily contingent upon administrative behaviors, especially in developing countries where systemic support is limited. Thus, communication training and leadership development should be a priority in improving school effectiveness.

Conclusions

The study concluded that school heads' communication styles—both passive and aggressive—significantly affected the emotional stress levels of secondary school teachers. Although the overall communication patterns were found to be moderate, they were not effective enough to support a psychologically safe and productive environment.

The regression analysis confirmed that these styles were key predictors of teacher stress, with aggressive communication posing a slightly higher risk than passive communication. Therefore, improving the communication behavior of school heads is essential for

promoting teachers' emotional well-being and fostering a healthy school climate. The findings highlight the importance of assertive and empathetic communication in educational leadership.

Recommendations

- Conduct regular training workshops for school heads on effective communication strategies, focusing on assertiveness, active listening, and emotional intelligence.
- Integrate communication modules into leadership certification programs to ensure that future school administrators adopt constructive communication styles.
- Establish anonymous feedback systems where teachers can report communication-related concerns without fear of retaliation.
- Offer specialized sessions on handling school-based conflicts through dialogue rather than avoidance or aggression.

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